

Acidity Functions of Indicators for High pH Range in Non-aqueous Medium. Part-IV

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α -*o*-Carboxyphenylazo-*p*-nitrobenzyl cyanide (OCPNBC) and α -*p*-carboxyphenylazo-*p*-nitrobenzyl cyanide (PCPNBC) having COOH group and α -*m*-sulphophenylazo-*p*-nitrobenzyl cyanide (MSPNBC), α -*p*-sulphophenylazo-*p*-nitrobenzyl cyanide (PSPNBC) having SO₃H group, have been investigated as acid-base indicators in ethanolic sodium ethoxide (ESE) medium. The autoprotolysis constant of ethanol¹ is 19.1. Ionisation constant of indicators, acidity function values are discussed².

Results and Discussion

Four indicators reported here exist as molecular species in acidic media. All are yellow in colour and their absorption maxima are within the range 410–420 nm. Extinction coefficient for molecular species are in the order, PSPNBC > PCPNBC > OCPNBC > MSPNBC, having values 1×10^4 to 0.9 to 10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ in ethanolic sodium ethoxide (ESE) medium. Monoanionic species are being formed as the pH is increased. The pK values are in the order, MSPNBC < PCPNBC < PSPNBC < OCPNBC. In most of the cases, the first isobestic point lies in shorter wavelength region and the second one is clearly seen.

Extinction coefficients of indicators in ethanol while in ethanolic sodium ethoxide are : for molecular species $\epsilon = 1 \times 10^4$ to 9×10^4 , for monoanionic species $\epsilon = 9 \times 10^3$ to 3.9×10^4 , and for dianionic species 3.7×10^4 to 1.25×10^5 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. In most of the cases isobestic points are clearly seen. In case of PSPNBC, isobestic point lies in shorter wavelength region. A band corresponding to molecular species lies around 410 to 420 nm, and for monoanionic species a band lies at 530–610

nm. The spectral characteristics are given in Table 1. The nature of absorption curve indicates that there is equilibrium between molecular and monoanionic, and monoanionic acid dianionic species.

The stock solutions of indicators do not show any measurable change over the period of one year and are quite stable. The solution in alkaline system show stability for several hours, thus enabling one to have sufficient time for experimental measurements.

Acidity functions were theoretically calculated on the basis of use of autoprotolysis constant of ethanol and ethanol H₂^M values calculated from the spectral data. The theoretical acidity functions plotted in the above show agreement with the practical values. Tables 1 and 2 give the acidity functions of four indicators. It can be seen that H^E-functions cover the range 14.13–16.70 and H₂^E-function the range 16.13–19.26. These values on comparison with the theoretical values reveal that first ionisation of OCPNBC, MSPNBC, PSPNBC, PCPNBC prove to be useful set for colorimetric determination.

Following conclusion could be drawn from the above results. (i) The indicators are structurally similar, hence their ionisation characteristics are similar. (ii) The proposed indicators are intensely coloured, the colour changes vivid and easily discernable, and possess suitable colour characteristics. (iii) In alkaline medium the indicators are soluble in ethanolic and methanolic media. It is possible to extend the use of the indicators to other non-aqueous systems also. (iv) Sufficiently wide range of alkalinity in both the media ethanol and methanol,

TABLE 1—ABSORPTION CHARACTERISTICS OF INDICATORS IN ETHANOLIC SODIUM ETHOXIDE

Indicator	Mono-anionic pK ₁	Di-anionic pK ₂	$\lambda_{\max}(\text{nm})$			$\epsilon (\text{dm}^3\text{mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1})$			Colour change	Isobestic Point(nm)	
			Mole- cular	Mono- anionic	Di- anionic	Mole- cular	Mono- anionic	Di- anionic		(1)	(2)
OCPNBC	16.10	18.30	420	610	540	9×10^4	2.4×10^4	1.23×10^5	Yellow to green to blue	Uv	460
PCPNBC	14.07	16.90	410	570	550	1.5×10^4	9×10^3	3.7×10^4	Yellow to violet	Uv	460
MSPNBC	15.81	18.01	410	610	560	4.5×10^4	3.9×10^4	8.4×10^4	Yellow to green to blue	Uv	450
PSPNBC	14.92	17.51	400	500	530	1×10^4	2×10^4	6.5×10^4	Yellow to red to violet	Uv	450

from 10^{-5} to 1 M alkali, covers practically entire range of alkalinity encountered in reactions in alkaline media.

Acidity function in methanolic sodium methoxide, $\text{H}^{\text{E-}}$ and $\text{H}_2^{\text{E-}}$, corresponding to first and second proton loss are evaluated (Table 1). Acidity functions in ethanolic sodium ethoxide are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ACIDITY FUNCTION IN ETHANOLIC SODIUM ETHOXIDE

Indicator	Medium	$\text{H}^{\text{E-}}$	$\text{H}_2^{\text{E-}}$
OCPNBC	MSM	14.00–15.90	17.31–18.96
PCPNBC	ESE	14.13–15.09	16.13–18.04
MSPNBC	ESE	15.13–16.37	17.53–19.26
PSPNBC	ESE	15.99–16.70	16.95–18.28

Experimental

A Beckman DU2 spectrophotometer with matched pair of 10 mm glass cuvettes and a Radiometer pHM4 pH-meter with glass-calomel electrode combination were used.

Indicators were prepared according to the procedure in literature⁵.

Procedure : A 0.05% (w/v) solution of each

indicator was prepared. The sodium ethoxide of various concentrations were prepared to adjust the desired pH⁶. The final concentration of the indicator was 1.6×10^{-5} M. Absorption spectrum of the indicator was measured. Acidity functions and specific colour discrimination were done⁷. Absorbance at intermediate pH values was used to determine the ratio of anionic and molecular forms from which the pK values were calculated⁸.

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